

The study plan

Spatial GIS-analysis of the long-term dynamics in the environmental changes in reindeer pastures, Lapland, northern Finland

The research stay of Ms Polina Lemenkova at the *University of Lapland, Arctic Centre*, is supposed under the supervision of the Research professor Dr. B. Forbes from the 01 March 2011 until 01 September 2011 (six months).

a. Introduction: research problem

Reindeer are unique part of the northern environmental in Lapland. For the comfortable existing they need large areas of herding pastures for grazing. The anthropogenic activities may influence the ecosystems where pastures are based in a negative way: mining, logging, oil and gas exploration, hydro power development as well as other human activities encroaching to the traditional habitats of reindeers and threatening the herding areas. Finally, climate changes influence natural environment and biodiversity of the northern ecosystems. All these factors lead to negative changes in the structure of landscapes, patterns defragmentation, decrease of biodiversity, and worsening of life conditions for the reindeer existence. The dynamics of these changes must be evaluated for the monitoring and sustainable development of the unique Lappish landscapes in the northern Finland. The proposed research focuses on the spatial GIS analysis and raster-based mapping of the changes in landscapes and land cover in the areas of reindeer herding pastures in High Arctic (Finnish Lapland).

b. Objectives and aims of the research

The main purpose and aim of the research is to detect trends in the state of geographical and environmental conditions of the northern ecosystems during the past 40 years (since 1970-s). The research objectives are spatial analysis and mapping of the land cover classes in northern Finland in the context of the protection and monitoring of the northern environment in Lappish ecosystems.

The technical implementation of the research will be based on (i) *ArcGIS 9.3* software as a major tool for spatial analysis and cartographic presentation, (ii) *ENVI* software for the raster processing and analyzing geospatial imagery and (iii) *DIVA-GIS* freeware for biodiversity assessment and mapping (<http://www.diva-gis.org/>).

GIS-based spatial analysis will be used for detecting and mapping areas of different land cover classes in Lapland and their changes in time. The raster images processing will be based on scenes from *Landsat TM* and *ETM+* downloaded from USGS free service (e.g., USGS GloVis, <http://glovis.usgs.gov/> NOAA, etc) for the several years in the same summer periods (ideally from 1970-s up to now).

The objective of the raster analysis is the investigation of the distribution of different land cover classes in Lappish landscapes over period of 30-40 years (depending on availability of suitable satellite images). The dynamics in trends of changes will be used for the forecasting and prognosis of the probable future situation in northern ecosystems, as well as analysis of their response towards the environmental and climate changes in high North.

c. Working plan and methods to be applied (including a time schedule)

01.03.-30.03.2011. Data collecting and treatment

Collecting, management and organizing of the geographical and environmental data of the Lappish ecosystems into main GIS-project, using *ArcCatalog* module of *ArcGIS* from existent free open sources (satellite images, available vector maps) or/and available resources of the *Arctic Centre, University of Lapland* (available vector or scanned maps, results of fieldwork). This initial yet important part of research work includes organising spatial data to assemble connections to all existing necessary GIS data, maps and raster images, and storing them in a folder on a local disk and in personal Geodatabase standard format in *ArcCatalog*. This part of work also includes georeferencing of all data using *ArcMap* projecting and setting up coordinate systems of some data (where necessary). Organizing data into GIS projects and creating of main GIS-project and Geodatabase will be implemented on *ArcGIS9.3*. The logically organized data, collected together in one GIS project, will also enable easy access for the work for further researchers.

01.04.-30.05.2011 Data processing and GIS-mapping

The raster images processing will be based on scenes from *Landsat TM* and *ETM+* downloaded from USGS free service (e.g., USGS GloVis, NOAA, etc) for the several years in the same summer periods (ideally from 1970-s up to now). Raster-based spatial analysis will be used for the mapping of changes in the land cover patterns by comparing differences of areas on the images using bands combinations, masking and estimation of these changes in the areas. It includes supervised classification with training sites of different patterns on the landscapes (10-15 set areas) using bands for green, red, NIR and combination of NIR/red bands. *ArcGIS* spatial analysis will be used for land cover mapping in different years. DIVA-GIS is mainly suggested for biodiversity mapping: species distribution within the region of research, species and genera diversity in Lappish ecosystems (using free pool of genetic data of the *System-wide Information Network for Genetic Resources (SINGER)*, <http://singer.cgiar.org/index.jsp>).

01.06.-30.06.2011 Environmental analysis

The environmental analysis of the ecosystems in Lapland using available data, materials and maps focusing on environment, biogeochemistry and ecology of the region and cooperation / discussions with other scientists:

- ✓ Critical processes determining and influencing changes in Lappish ecosystems (contamination, climate change, impacts of human activities)
- ✓ Effects of the processes of climate and environmental change on the state and conditions of the habitats of reindeers
- ✓ Monitoring and assessment of dynamics in land cover changes based on history of past changes and conditions of present state
- ✓ Assessment of biodiversity in Lapland region: genera distribution and species diversity over northern Finland
- ✓ Forecasting of the possible future consequences of the land cover changes in high North for reindeer habitats

01.07.-31.08.2011 Preparing research results for publishing in two articles

The results of the data analysis (July-August 2011) will contain series of thematic environmental maps of the Lappish ecosystems, maps detecting land cover changes (based on raster classification) and landscapes monitoring based on the processing and spatial analysis of the collected data. The main results will be reported in two articles focusing on following aspects:

- (i) *ENVI* techniques of raster images processing applied for environmental monitoring and changes in land cover classes
- (ii) Spatial analysis of the dynamics and forecasting of ecosystem changes in Lapland using *ArcGIS9.3* and assessment of biodiversity using *DIVA-GIS*.

d. Expected results

- The GIS-project containing pool of vector and raster layers with environmental and geographic data
- Layouts with thematic maps of biodiversity and ecosystems
- Raster maps (results of satellite images processing and classification of land cover patterns within landscapes)
- Two articles for publishing, containing main results of the research

e. Usefulness

The organisation and establishment of GIS-project “Changes in Lappish ecosystems” enable environmental analysis and modelling and is applicable in several scientific geospatial fields including the followings:

- *Cartography and GIS*: Mapping and detecting changes in the state of Lappish ecosystem since 1970-s: habitats fragmentation, changes in land cover classes and patterns of the landscapes
- *Geochemistry*: analysis of the dynamics of the environmental changes: values of the concentrations of contaminants, origin and ways transport of heavy metal within the ecosystems in several years
- *Biology*: assessment of the biodiversity (species and genera diversity) within ecosystems, modelling of species distribution
- *Ecology*: environmental monitoring in the region of Lapland, mapping reindeer habitats development and changes within the region

The proposed plan fits well the research themes of the *Arctic Global Change* group, University of Lapland. The theme of studying the ecology is challenging, because unique northern ecosystems of Lapland are of high environmental importance, being vital habitat landscapes for reindeers and essential part of the global planet environment. Establishment the contacts and connections between scientists and universities is necessary for the strengthening of cooperation in projects of such international importance as environmental protection in the high North.

Ms Lemenkova suites well for the proposed research project, because she has both knowledge of environment and geosciences, and strong technical skills in GIS. She studied geosciences in different European universities, participated in the environmental research in Polar regions (Antarctic expedition and studies of the Arctic ecosystems in BSc diploma), and had successful 3-month visiting research stay at the University of Kuopio in 2009. Therefore, we warmly support her CIMO-Scholarship application for the proposed visiting stay at the *University of Lapland, Arctic Global Change* research group since 01.03.2011 until 01.09.2011 under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Bruce Forbes.